

Mineral chemistry and *in-situ* U-Pb geochronology of altered pegmatite from the vicinity of the Strashimir Pb-Zn vein deposit

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Abstract. The current study presents new mineralogical, geochemical and geochronological data for a pegmatite body hosted in gneisses and marbles from the vicinity of the Strashimir Pb-Zn vein deposit, Madan ore district, South Bulgaria. The mineral composition of the studied pegmatite is represented by oligoclase–andesine (An_{10.1–33.2}) and albite (An_{0–7.6}), which prevail over K-feldspar (Or_{87.9–92.4}), and quartz. The established accessory minerals are allanite-(Ce), titanite, apatite and zircon. The pegmatite/marble contact is affected by later hydrothermal silicate-carbonate alteration without detected ore mineralization, despite the spatial proximity with the Strashimir Pb-Zn vein deposit. Epidote-group minerals in pegmatite are defined as members of the clinozoisite–epidote series. As a major constituent of the hydrothermal alteration zone, they are manifested in two well-distinguished generations along with chlorite, quartz and carbonates. The calculated temperature of chlorite mineralization yields T° of crystallization in the range of 223–266 °C. As a result of the hydrothermal fluid circulation, the accessory allanite-(Ce) is transformed to REE-rich epidote-clinozoisite, marked by depletion of REE and Fe and enrichment of Si, Al, and Ca. Due to the limited mobility of REE in fluids, after leaching these elements are incorporated in nearby crystallized epidotes. According to the occurrence, mineral association and chemical properties, three titanite populations are distinguished in the pegmatite. Two of them were *in-situ* dated by the LA-ICP-MS U-Pb method and reveal overlapping ages of 39.9±2.1 Ma and 39.5±2.2 Ma (39.3±1.2 Ma combining all titanite analyses). The ages are interpreted as titanite growth in a pegmatite body related to granitic melts in the Late Alpine high-metamorphic units (Madan Unit) of the Central Rhodopes. Hydrothermal fluids either did not affect the U-Pb isotope system of the titanites or were derived from the same fluid-rich melt.

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INTRODUCTION

Recently, the interest in pegmatites as a source of industrial materials and critical elements enforces and encourages the revision and supplementary investigation in pegmatite regions (Linnen *et al.*, 2012; Saleh

et al., 2019; Kamar *et al.*, 2021). Abundant pegmatite bodies with different sizes, shapes and positions are major rock constituents intruded in the metamorphic complex, which hosts the main vein and metasomatic Pb-Zn ore mineralization (including 50 deposits and 39 occurrences) in the Central Rhodopes, South

Bulgaria. Initial study, describing microclinal pegmatites from the region, was presented by Dimitrov and Kotev (1967). Mineralogical, geochemical and geochronological data on various pegmatite bodies were given by Arnaudov *et al.* (1969, 1990a, b), Ivanov (1991), Cherneva *et al.* (1995). Recent ongoing studies in the Pb-Zn deposits have been focused on the pegmatite mineral composition (Vassileva *et al.*, 2021). Data about the mineral association in pegmatite bodies from Krushev Dol, Dzhrukovo and Govedarnika Pb-Zn deposits were reported by Vassileva *et al.* (2022), Y. Georgieva *et al.* (2022) and S. Georgieva *et al.* (2022a). Some hydrothermally altered pegmatites from the Petrovitsa deposit have been studied in terms of mineralogy and U-Pb geochronology on magmatic and hydrothermal titanite (Milenkov *et al.*, 2020, 2022). In the same deposit, Hantsche *et al.* (2021) pointed out the occurrence of two epidote generations, owing to the hydrothermal processes and skarn formation in marbles and aluminosilicate rocks.

Near the Strashimir Pb-Zn vein deposit, a large pegmatite body is hosted between gneisses and marbles. It is spatially situated (and outcrops) above the main ore vein of the deposit. The subject of this research is the clarification of the mineral composition and estimation of potential minerals-concentrators of critical elements. To achieve the aim of this study, mineralogical and geochemical data for epidote, chlorite, titanite, allanite and apatite are presented. The *in-situ* U/Pb ages of the pegmatite-hosted titanites and chlorite geothermometry complement the interpretation of the processes' evolution in the studied pegmatite.

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

Regional geology

The Rhodopes are the main tectonic unit on the Balkan Peninsula often referred to as the Rhodope Zone, Rhodope Massif and, lately, Rhodope Metamorphic Complex (RMC). Tectonic interpretations agree on its complex Alpine (Late Jurassic to late Oligocene) tectono-metamorphic history comprising earlier compressional and later extensional periods (*e.g.*, Dinter and Royden, 1993; Burg, 2012; Froitzheim *et al.*, 2014; Ivanov, 2017; Schmid *et al.*, 2020). The compressional tectonics resulted in the formation of a nappe stack. Following the regional-scale tectonic model proposed by Georgiev *et al.* (2010), Jahn-Awe *et al.* (2012) and Froitzheim *et al.* (2014), the RMC is composed of four large,

orogen-scale allochthonous thrust sheets, namely: Lower, Middle, Upper and Uppermost allochthons. The Alpine orogeny was polycyclic, with episodes of subduction and crustal accretion (Gautier *et al.*, 2017). The collision and the south-verging thrusting started in Jurassic–Cretaceous times (*e.g.*, Burg, 2012) but finished only in mid to late Eocene time and was still active in the lower part of the nappe system when the higher part of the nappe pile was tectonically denuded (Jahn-Awe *et al.*, 2010, 2012; Georgiev *et al.*, 2010; Gorinova *et al.*, 2020).

During the Late Alpine evolution of the RMC in Southern Bulgaria and Northern Greece, the processes of postcollisional extension generated detachment faults, syndeformational sedimentary basins and exhumation of large metamorphic core complexes (MCCs) (Kaiser Rohrmeier *et al.*, 2013). The Madan ore field and the studied pegmatite vein are situated in the hanging wall of the Central Rhodopean dome (CRD), interpreted as such MCC. The Late Alpine postcollisional evolution of the CRD started with the intrusion of granitic bodies at ~43–41 Ma (*e.g.*, Smilyan and Yugovo plutons), probably marking the beginning of the extension and core complex formation (Ovtcharova *et al.*, 2003; Raeva *et al.*, 2008; Kaiser Rohrmeier *et al.*, 2013). The Smilyan pluton intruded in the metamorphic rocks of the Madan Unit (43.4±1.41 Ma, Ovtcharova *et al.*, 2003; 41.92±0.22 Ma, Kaiser-Rohrmeier, 2005). The early stages of extension were characterized by normal faulting, rotation of fault blocks and thinning that caused cooling of the hanging wall by ~300 °C at about 40 Ma to 38 Ma (Kaiser Rohrmeier *et al.*, 2013). Kounov *et al.* (2020) also suggested a rapid cooling setting between ~37 Ma and ~33 Ma. In the footwall, high metamorphic temperatures and decompression persisted and resulted in partial melting and formation of migmatites at 37 Ma and pegmatites at ~36 Ma (Ovtcharova *et al.*, 2003). The emplacement of rhyolite porphyry dykes and the extrusion of volcanic products deposited on top of the exposed center of the dome marked the final cooling of CRD at about 33 Ma to 30 Ma. Kaiser Rohrmeier *et al.* (2013) suggested that the formation of the Pb-Zn deposits at 31–29 Ma was generated by large-scale hydrothermal fluid circulation, driven by the high heat flow attending core complex formation, exhumation and final fracturing of a rapidly thinned crust.

Local geology

The studied pegmatite vein is in the vicinity of Strashimir Village (Fig. 1) and intrudes the variegated succession of high metamorphic rocks with

Fig. 1. District-scale geological map with deposit locations (modified after Hantsche *et al.*, 2021, and references therein) and applied map of the tectonic units of Bulgaria (modified from Ivanov, 2017). The red rectangle corresponds to the studied area.

Jurassic protolithic age, *i.e.*, the gneisses, amphibolites and marbles referred to the Madan Unit (Sarov *et al.*, 2006, 2010; Raeva and Cherneva, 2008; Raeva *et al.*, 2008; Jahn-Awe *et al.*, 2012) of the Middle Allochthone of RMC. The same unit hosts the main ore bodies of the Madan ore field. Numerous pegmatite bodies were intruded into the metamorphic sequence of the Madan Unit. These dykes are concordant or oblique to the foliation in the metamorphic frame. The pegmatites from the region suffered intense hydrothermal alteration during hydrothermal ore deposition. Their time of intrusion is estimated by the calculated U-Pb weighted average age on magmatic titanites at 48.9 ± 2.3 Ma, while the pegmatite-hosted hydrothermal titanites are dated at

39.2 ± 1.5 Ma (Petrovitsa Pb-Zn deposit; Milenkov *et al.*, 2020, 2022). The present study is focused on a well-exposed pegmatite body outcropping in the area of the Pechinsko Pass, close to the upper part of the Strashimir Pb-Zn vein deposit. It represents a large dyke, more than 2 m thick, emplaced along the contact between marbles and gneisses with amphibolite lenses (Fig. 2). The body lies concordantly between gneisses and marbles without clear deformation signs according to field observations. Field observations determined the epidote-group minerals as one of the major constituents of the altered pegmatites (see Fig. 2). The epidote hydrothermal alteration halo, developed in the pegmatite along the contact with the marble, is fluctuating, with a

Fig. 2. Photograph of the studied pegmatite outcrop near the Pechinsko pass on top of the Strashimir Pb-Zn vein deposit.

thickness of up to 40 cm. Similar alteration halo is absent in the volume of the marble. The outcrop is situated near the plane of a low-angle subhorizontal fault assigned as Madan detachment (Sarov *et al.*, 2006). The latter separates the Madan Unit from the partly migmatized Carboniferous–Permian orthogneisses with amphibolite lenses of the Arda Unit (Lower Allochthon), building the core (and footwall) of CRD (Cherneva and Georgieva, 2005; Ivanov, 2017). The Madan detachment is not directly dated, but some constrains are made by the timing of the Startsevo-Ardino Shear Zone merging the core (footwall) of CRD in its eastern part. The time frame for the activity of this shear zone is determined by U-Pb zircon dating of a pre-tectonic pegmatite and a post-tectonic granitoid body within the zone that yielded ages of ~45 Ma and ~36 Ma, respectively (Jahn-Awe *et al.*, 2012). In the time of the ore deposition in the Madan ore field at 31–29 Ma, the Madan detachment is interpreted as pre-ore and screening the ore-bearing fluids.

SAMPLES AND METHODS

Thin-sections of representative pegmatite samples from the altered zone close to the contact with the

marble and from the innermost visibly unaltered part of the pegmatite were studied by optical microscopy, SEM-EDS and LA-ICP-MS. The mineral relationships were observed in transmitted light on a Leica DM750P at the Geological Institute (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences) and selected spots were subsequently investigated in BSE-regime by a JEOL JSM-6010PLUS/LA (University of Mining and Geology) and JEOL JSM-6390 (Institute of Physical Chemistry, BAS). The chemical composition of minerals was determined using a Hitachi S-3400N SEM equipped with an Oxford Instruments Energy Dispersive Spectrometer X-Max20. The spectra were processed automatically with the AzTec Energy software package using the TrueQ method at the “Geomodel” Resource Center of St. Petersburg State University. Shooting parameters: accelerating voltage was 20 kV, beam current was 1.7 nA, working distance was 10 mm, acquisition time was 30 s in spot-mode. Quantification of elemental compositions was conducted using standard samples of natural and synthetic compounds, such as Y glass (Y), La glass (La), kyanite (Al), titanium oxide (Ti), Ce glass (Ce), forsterite (Mg), Th dioxide (Th), quartz (Si), rhodonite (Mn), Nb glass (Nb), wollastonite (Ca), InP (P), albite (Na), orthoclase (K) and ferric oxide (Fe).

U-Pb titanite geochronology and major, minor and trace element analyses of the minerals were performed, using the LA-ICP-MS system at the Geological Institute, BAS, consisting of New Wave Research (NWR) 193 nm Excimer laser UP-193FX attached to a Perkin-Elmer ELAN DRC-e quadrupole inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer. Laser frequency of 6 Hz and 25–50 μm laser ablation craters were applied. NIST 610 and MKED1 (Spandler *et al.*, 2016) standard reference materials were used as external standards for element concentration and dating, respectively. In order to recalculate the titanite age, the common ^{207}Pb correction was applied (Andersen, 2002). SEM-EDS-measured SiO_2 content in studied minerals was used as an internal standard.

The structural formulae of epidote-group minerals were calculated, based on 12.5 oxygen atoms and 8 cations. The Fe^{3+} was recalculated to the charge-balanced formula, based on the stoichiometric criteria proposed by Droop (1987). The structural formulae of chlorites were calculated on the basis of 28 oxygen atoms; $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ and OH were calculated assuming full site occupancy.

RESULTS

Mineral relationships

The mineral composition of the studied pegmatite is mainly constituted by feldspars and quartz. According to our observations, plagioclases, represented by oligoclase–andesine ($\text{An}_{10.1-33.2}$) and albite ($\text{An}_{0-7.6}$), prevail over K-feldspar ($\text{Or}_{87.9-92.4}$), and the quartz quantity is about 20–25% of the rock volume. Allanite, titanite, apatite and zircon are among the established accessory minerals. Profile sampling across a selected pegmatite body did not show clear zonal distribution of the minerals. The plagioclase and K-feldspar form coarse-grained aggregates, whereas the quartz usually forms irregularly distributed medium- to fine-grained anhedral grains, often occupying the interstitial space between plagioclase and K-feldspar. Thin network of late calcite, sericite and chlorite are often observed in the feldspars. Normally, albite occurs along with the aforementioned later association, suggesting its hydrothermal origin. The overprinted pervasive hydrothermal mineralization in the pegmatite is observed along the contact with marble, forming a well-developed zone of replacement (up to 40 cm), veins and nests. The main mineral association established in this zone is

composed of epidotes, chlorite, quartz, carbonates, hematite and scarce clinopyroxene.

Titanite is developed in variable sizes and shapes (Fig. 3). Generally, it is observed as sub- to euhedral crystals, often as anhedral grains (up to 1 mm) in association with feldspars, quartz, apatite, allanite, clinopyroxene and chlorite (assigned as population 1; Fig. 3a–d). Parts of the crystals are deformed, cracked (a sign of brittle deformation) or folded (ductile deformation; Fig. 3c). A second population of titanite (population 2) is presented as well formed, mostly euhedral, with common wedge-shaped habit and tiny size (up to 30–40 μm), mainly associated with chlorite replacing clinopyroxene ($X_{\text{Fe}} = 0.26-0.44$) (Fig. 3e). In the hydrothermal zone (close to the contact with marbles), a third titanite population (population 3) is established both as anhedral crystals enclosed in epidote matrix and as euhedral crystals (up to 3 mm long) in the cavities between the prismatic epidote crystals filled also with chlorite and carbonate (Fig. 3f–h). Weak zoning, mainly owing to the chemical variation, could be outlined by back scattered electron (BSE) observation (Fig. 3h).

The allanite typically forms up to 1 mm dark brown single euhedral to subhedral crystals among grains of feldspar and/or quartz or within epidote masses in the alteration zone (Fig. 4). Distinct patchy or irregular zonal patterns in the allanite crystals is observed (Fig. 4e–h). In general, its outward zones are marked with traces of dissolution and recrystallization. Frequently, the mineral is replaced on the periphery or fragmented and intersected by late hydrothermal epidote (Fig. 4b–d, g, h). Apatite (up to 600 μm) and zircon (up to 200 μm) occur as sub- to euhedral crystals in association with the aforementioned minerals (Figs 3d, e, 4c–f).

The epidotes represent an essential hydrothermal product that is a result of multiphase mineral formation developed in two generations, distinguished texturally, chemically and by color (Fig. 5). The occurrence, association and morphology of the studied epidotes indicate significant similarity with the properties of others observed in the nearby deposits (*e.g.*, Petrovitsa), developed in pegmatites as well. These epidote-group minerals are also presented in two hydrothermal generations, predominantly as clinozoisite, rarely reaching epidote end members (Georgieva *et al.*, 2021; Georgieva *et al.*, 2022b). The obvious exception is the size of the studied epidote crystals exceeding here 5 cm. Elongated prismatic crystals, clusters or radiating aggregates arranged in nests and veins are typical. The color of the mineral is red to deep pink or yellow to pistachio green (Fig. 5a–d). Single crystals exhibit color vari-

Fig. 3. Occurrence of titanite and apatite: *a*) CPL microphotograph of titanite (population 1), apatite and allanite among feldspars replaced by calcite, sericite and chlorite; *b–d*) BSE images of titanite (populations 1 and 2 – outside of the epidote alteration zone) and apatite in assemblage with allanite and altered feldspars; *e*) BSE image of titanite (population 2) crystals in association with chlorite developed on the altered clinopyroxene; *f*) CPL microphotograph of titanite (population 3) with epidote, quartz, calcite and chlorite; *g, h*) BSE images of the analyzed titanite crystals (population 3). The white circles show some of the SEM-EDS analysis locations, whereas the red circles show LA-ICP-MS analysis locations. Abb.: Ttn – titanite; Ap – apatite; Aln – allanite; Zir – zircon; Pl – plagioclase; Kfs – K-feldspar; Qz – quartz; Cpx – clinopyroxene; Ep – epidote; Cal – calcite; Chl – chlorite.

Fig. 4. Occurrence of allanite: macrophotographs of allanite in association with feldspars and quartz from the pegmatite outside the alteration zone (a) and with epidote and quartz from the alteration zone (b); c, d) CPL microphotographs of allanite overgrown by epidote along with apatite in matrix of altered feldspars; e–g) BSE images of allanite and associated titanite, apatite, feldspars, chlorite and quartz outside the alteration zone; h) allanite enclosed and intersected by epidote from the alteration zone. Abbreviations and symbols: same as in Fig. 3.

Fig. 5. Occurrence of epidote: *a*) macrophotograph of both epidote generations (pink Ep1 and green Ep2) along with chlorite and quartz from the alteration zone, developed in pegmatite; *b*) CPL microphotograph of both epidote generations in association with quartz and titanite. The growth of the second (Ep2) generation over the first (Ep1) can be observed.; *c*, *d*) binocular magnifier image of both epidote generations – pink (Ep1) and green (Ep2); *e*, *f*) BSE images of *c* and *d* respectively, showing distinct boundary between both generations; *g*) BSE images showing clear oscillatory zoning in epidote due to Al/Fe variation; *h*) BSE image of epidote 2 growing on epidote 1. Abbreviations and symbols: same as in Fig. 3.

ation from red in the core to green towards the rim (see Fig. 5c). The early epidote generation generally occurs as sub- to euhedral, short prismatic deep pink to red single crystals or crystalline clusters in veins and nests. The crystals show clear oscillatory zoning in BSE images due to the Al/Fe chemical heterogeneity. The brighter zones reflect higher Fe content (Fig. 5e–g). The second epidote generation occurs mainly as pistachio green, sub- to euhedral, elongated prismatic crystals and radiating aggregates overgrowing or crosscutting the first epidote generation (see Fig. 5). Fine-grained dark green chlorite, sub- to euhedral calcite, sub- to euhedral titanite and later quartz generally complete the epidote association (see Figs 3f–h, 4h, 5). In the studied hydrothermal zone, the pegmatite minerals are preserved only as relics. Accessory sub- to euhedral allanite, titanite (see Figs 3f–h, 5b), apatite and K-feldspar with irregular shapes are observed among epidotes. Allanite is fragmented and wrapped by later epidote mineralization (see Fig. 4b, h). Except for pyrite, sulphide mineralization is not observed in the studied samples, despite the spatial nearness to the Strashimir vein with rich Pb-Zn ores.

Mineral chemistry and trace-element signature

As mentioned above, three populations of titanite are established according to their occurrence and morphology. The chemical composition of titanites observed in the pegmatite outside the epidote-dominated alteration zone (populations 1 and 2) clearly differs from that of the epidote-associated titanites in the hydrothermal zone (population 3).

The discussed wt.% and ppm contents of oxides and elements listed in the text represent the summary data from all available analyses. In the included tables, only representative SEM-EDS and LA-ICP-MS analyses are given. The incorporation of Al_2O_3 in population 1 is up to 2.44 wt.%, while Fe_2O_3 is up to 1.25 wt.%. Yttrium and Nb are detectable only by LA-ICP-MS and reach up to 2851 ppm and 1954 ppm, respectively (Tables 1, 2). Significant, but fewer, incorporations of V, Zr and U compared to epidote-associated titanites are detected. The ΣREE ranges from 620 ppm to 6543 ppm. Chondrite-normalized pattern of these titanites shows relative depletion of HREE compared to LREE and

Table 1
SEM-EDS representative analyses of titanite (wt.%)

Sample	Pch1p-2066	Pch1p-2067	Pch1p-2107	Pch1p-2048	Pch1p-2060	Pch1p-2118	Pch2a-2015	Pch2a-2016	Pch2a-2012
Details	population 1			population 2			population 3		
	grain 1		grain 2	crystal 1	crystal 2	crystal 3	one crystal		
	core	rim					core	rim	rim
SiO ₂	29.91	30.46	30.69	31.21	31.09	31.3	30.76	31.31	30.16
TiO ₂	37.34	36.44	38.19	37.26	37.22	37.07	33.46	35	32.63
Al ₂ O ₃	1.91	1.97	1.69	1.87	1.98	2.26	2.96	2.96	3.75
FeO	1.04	1.19	0.79	0.73	1.25	1.01	1.51	1.07	1.69
Nb ₂ O ₅							1.76	0.94	1.54
CaO	28.43	28.23	28.32	28.47	28.7	28.75	27.45	28.5	27.09
MnO				0.14					
Y ₂ O ₃							1.56	0.92	2.62
Total	98.63	98.29	99.68	99.69	100.24	100.39	99.46	100.70	99.48
<i>apfu</i>									
Si	0.996	1.016	1.007	1.022	1.017	1.019	1.023	1.022	1.009
Ti	0.935	0.914	0.942	0.918	0.915	0.908	0.837	0.859	0.821
Al	0.075	0.077	0.065	0.072	0.076	0.087	0.116	0.114	0.148
Fe	0.013	0.015	0.010	0.009	0.015	0.012	0.019	0.013	0.021
Nb							0.026	0.014	0.023
Σ	1.023	1.006	1.017	0.999	1.007	1.007	0.999	1.000	1.013
Ca	1.014	1.009	0.995	0.999	1.006	1.003	0.978	0.996	0.971
Mn				0.004					
Y							0.028	0.016	0.047
Σ	1.014	1.009	0.995	1.003	1.006	1.003	1.006	1.012	1.017

clear positive Eu anomaly (Fig. 6a). The Th/U ratio is between 0.12–6.23 (indicating the origin of the mineral – Gao *et al.*, 2012), Dy/Yb_N (0.66–2.29, suggesting HREE depletion or enrichment with respect to MREE – Scibiorski *et al.*, 2019), Lu/Hf (0.14–1.38, suggesting the type of origin – Li *et al.*, 2010). An ambivalent signature in the frame of one of the studied grains with documented variation in the REE contents was established (Fig. 6b). In the second zone of this anhedral grain, a relative depletion of HREE compared to LREE and clear positive Eu anomaly comparable to titanites found in association with feldspars is observed. In the first zone, the REE signature shows a relatively flat pattern with negative Eu anomaly (characteristic for the epidote-associated titanite described below). These properties could be a sign of the crystallization sequence and the timing of titanite formation relative to other minerals.

The chemistry of the chlorite-associated titanites (population 2) shows a similar trend to popu-

lation 1, except for minor Mn incorporation up to 0.14 wt.% in single analyses (see Table 1). Trace-element chemistry by LA-ICP-MS was impossible because of the small crystal size (30–40 μm).

The chemical composition of population 3 titanites observed in the hydrothermal zone in association with epidote, chlorite and calcite reveals incorporation of Al₂O₃ up to 4.36 wt.%, Fe₂O₃ (1.94 wt.%) and Y₂O₃ (3.55 wt.%), which distinguish them chemically from populations 1 and 2 titanites observed in the pegmatite (see Table 1). Considerable incorporation of Nb is established as well. In certain titanite crystal zones, the Nb₂O₅ content reaches up to 5.22 wt.%. The ΣREE ranges from 2835 ppm to 12,719 ppm. Significant incorporation of Ta, Sn, Zr, V, Th and U is detected as well (see Table 2). Chondrite-normalized pattern shows relative depletion of LREE compared to HREE and clear negative Eu anomaly (Fig. 6c). The Th/U ratio is between 0.11–1.22, Lu/Hf (0.43–1.69), Dy/Yb_N (0.49–1.47).

Fig. 6. Chondrite-normalized REE patterns of titanite out of the alteration zone (a, b), and from the alteration zone (c). Normalization values after Sun and McDonough (1989).

Table 2

LA-ICP-MS representative analyses of titanite, allanite – REE-rich clinozoisite and epidote (ppm). The data of population 1 titanite referred to the crystal shown in Fig. 6b.

Sample	Pch1p-a14	Pch1p-a15	Pch1p-a21	Pch2a-d6	Pch2a-d8	Pch2a-d11	Pch1p-b11	Pch1p-b12	Pch1p-b13
Details	titanite outside the alteration zone (population 1)			titanite in the alteration zone (population 3)			allanite – REE-rich clinozoisite outside the alteration zone		
	zone 1	zone 1	zone 2	rim	rim	core	core	rim	rim
Li							<28.68	<25.47	<26.22
Be							<2.65	<11.94	<7.95
B							53.20	50.90	37.70
Sc	4.09	4.27	4.44	6.58	15.45	8.18	98.63	51.64	94.96
V	441.54	447.90	545.08	405.92	411.56	436.23	367.58	303.07	303.37
Cr							<25.58	41.76	49.39
Co							5.12	4.16	3.40
Ni	87.32	121.33	102.66	229.27	197.98	217.65	13.67	<23.56	<33.35
Cu							<3.43	<2.71	<3.83
Zn	8.70	9.98	11.57	24.94	23.07	25.16	211.69	190.55	170.74
Ga	44.52	51.78	34.41	36.69	38.69	27.77	2180.87	1776.19	1994.95
Ge	96.51	106.64	52.07	73.87	74.98	46.77	2112.18	1563.33	1777.63
As							240.61	180.44	197.72
Rb							<0.50	0.19	<0.48
Sr	34.34	36.17	50.42	24.94	27.78	23.99	530.38	376.50	466.56
Y	2560.83	2565.83	638.78	9793.86	22250.88	9053.50	673.73	560.09	721.47
Zr	405.85	384.85	1040.19	1081.87	2631.68	1329.92	9.89	13.14	8.76
Nb	1592.58	1946.31	280.59	8494.75	13861.87	7623.23	<0.34	<0.47	<0.46
Mo	13.12	18.68	12.69	10.01	6.80	12.82	<2.24	<2.65	<3.07
Ag							<0.80	<0.73	<0.95
Cd							<1.13	<4.32	<5.00
In							1.79	1.81	1.93
Sn	576.53	582.31	322.65	3144.58	3403.25	2055.47	13.55	26.66	14.41
Sb							<0.69	<0.82	<1.06
Cs							<0.18	<0.21	0.19
Ba							3.28	1.56	23.62
La	155.74	177.93	191.50	93.40	90.41	69.06	32112.74	24062.84	32383.16
Ce	765.99	878.48	670.47	498.71	468.44	366.53	62250.71	50652.55	58209.71
Pr	153.84	176.95	101.86	109.63	104.13	77.49	6459.27	4845.61	5541.17
Nd	832.39	944.41	452.37	645.82	629.40	452.69	20030.17	14652.23	16398.86
Sm	297.62	337.97	132.78	399.92	476.39	251.45	2435.60	1695.43	1963.03
Eu	65.06	71.74	51.77	43.13	37.69	39.45	265.99	151.66	214.24
Gd	319.03	350.04	114.30	758.16	1074.10	462.75	1179.30	888.86	1051.11
Tb	55.68	59.08	15.66	188.03	292.01	122.32	85.04	59.45	76.16
Dy	373.48	394.59	97.68	1546.38	2650.83	1097.13	272.21	188.77	244.61
Ho	83.05	83.72	19.67	370.82	684.06	281.30	32.00	22.11	31.89
Er	276.71	269.81	61.59	1215.17	2516.50	1052.00	47.83	40.37	49.67
Tm	43.02	42.11	9.37	186.78	427.17	181.27	5.07	4.27	4.94
Yb	296.07	288.92	65.75	1158.39	2900.72	1246.96	22.82	22.97	24.82
Lu	40.04	39.14	9.56	136.47	367.40	158.93	2.87	3.14	4.13
Hf	55.04	54.80	46.80	146.87	572.39	144.06	<0.75	0.92	0.89
Ta	88.08	87.41	4.16	1400.39	3543.63	1152.47	<0.21	0.10	<0.20
W	5.45	6.48	6.29	16.24	26.18	13.75	<0.33	<0.27	<1.94
Tl							<0.49	<0.31	<0.36
Pb	3.18	3.25	5.00	4.34	4.20	3.05	72.08	61.09	58.21
Bi							0.28	0.65	0.88
Th	94.13	95.24	91.36	97.21	199.28	146.09	10887.68	9140.25	8303.16
U	642.40	681.40	270.32	275.81	495.96	563.39	85.69	392.83	240.17

Table 2 (extension)

Sample	Pch2A-b4	Pch2A-b5	Pch2A-b6	Pch2A-c4	Pch2A-c5	Pch2A-c6	Pch1-e18	Pch2A-d12	Pch1-f9	Pch1-f6	Pch1-f4	Pch1-e14
Details	allanite – REE-rich clinozoisite in the alteration zone			green Ep close to Aln			pink Ep		zonal dichromatic long prism Ep		green Ep	
	rim	core	rim	grain	grain	grain	grain	long prism crystal	inner pink zone	outer green zone	grain	long prism crystal
Li	5.37	2.01	1.04	0.40	<2.37	<1.47	<0.51	0.55	0.75	<2.02	<2.38	0.60
Be	<2.59	<9.02	<2.32	<2.39	<4.69	<12.69	<12.98	<3.23	<3.36	<3.39	<3.29	<3.32
B	40.26	35.96	32.80	42.53	30.87	37.26	37.31	45.74	38.05	30.80	38.17	39.44
Sc	41.82	39.23	42.31	<1.74	<1.60	<1.62	1.62	<2.08	<1.85	<1.57	<1.47	<1.66
V	165.68	156.15	167.29	12.97	20.68	11.80	1.85	9.98	31.79	4.79	8.61	14.83
Cr	<15.39	<14.28	20.89	55.06	24.43	23.24	<16.06	<18.14	<16.93	<17.43	10.21	<12.87
Co	3.34	2.61	2.58	0.82	<0.58	0.51	3.22	6.56	3.16	<0.79	1.46	1.38
Ni	<4.21	<14.85	4.29	<4.28	<8.43	<4.87	<22.76	<5.87	<23.11	<5.96	<35.62	<5.76
Cu	<2.15	1.07	<2.16	<2.88	<2.83	0.68	0.83	<2.73	<0.77	<0.79	<2.75	<0.77
Zn	272.38	285.16	292.56	16.19	27.09	11.52	61.93	223.64	95.38	<4.40	<5.93	7.35
Ga	702.12	681.60	705.63	99.17	116.87	91.50	51.29	62.37	78.26	30.32	33.41	31.43
Ge	522.39	534.15	513.19	17.42	25.52	27.08	5.94	13.45	6.57	<6.86	9.50	3.36
As	65.73	62.58	63.84	6.99	4.35	8.50	<2.25	<3.47	<2.57	<2.61	<3.12	6.99
Rb	<0.29	<0.21	0.16	<0.31	<0.38	14.94	<0.31	<0.29	<0.30	<0.31	<0.28	<0.36
Sr	297.21	294.79	276.72	516.61	372.68	537.87	371.85	1116.82	348.74	719.52	352.68	539.25
Y	703.93	739.64	829.87	10.02	26.26	6.74	0.78	21.93	0.12	0.40	5.41	19.31
Zr	12.35	12.00	12.48	<0.40	0.28	<0.11	<0.13	8.22	<0.53	1.37	0.30	0.55
Nb	0.07	<0.22	0.06	0.53	0.60	0.07	0.81	12.50	1.14	<0.08	1.58	<0.28
Mo	<1.97	<0.40	<1.52	0.56	<2.00	<0.43	<2.05	<1.87	<2.64	<1.60	<2.39	<1.81
Ag	<0.14	<0.50	<0.13	<0.14	<0.76	<0.16	<0.19	<0.71	<0.75	<0.20	<0.90	<0.19
Cd	2.76	<2.78	<2.28	<4.41	<1.22	<2.54	<5.13	<4.78	<4.07	1.22	<5.05	<2.90
In	3.62	3.10	3.91	4.68	3.48	3.55	0.12	0.10	0.17	0.51	0.29	0.55
Sn	96.29	92.00	89.33	33.45	22.25	41.92	0.98	<0.92	2.12	2.01	<1.05	<1.17
Sb	<0.76	<0.84	<0.77	3.94	1.36	3.00	<0.15	0.70	0.28	<0.72	0.65	6.44
Cs	<0.13	<0.12	<0.03	0.41	0.10	1.37	<0.04	<0.05	<0.18	0.15	<0.05	0.08
Ba	1.44	1.46	1.29	1.75	0.74	28.65	2.79	39.23	2.21	1.04	1.18	1.35
La	16453.86	16330.50	16214.48	391.09	452.39	544.71	<0.25	1.63	<0.25	0.12	0.23	4.55
Ce	31510.75	31498.73	32455.79	1646.82	1951.97	1960.91	0.32	4.66	<0.06	0.33	0.58	9.53
Pr	2958.64	2922.34	2964.97	99.91	114.12	126.53	<0.20	0.48	<0.05	0.10	0.08	1.19
Nd	8546.70	8459.59	8618.75	191.53	198.94	251.75	<0.31	2.80	<0.32	<0.32	0.35	4.97
Sm	875.52	880.72	914.07	17.01	18.50	22.05	<0.37	1.69	<0.38	<1.18	<0.38	1.13
Eu	76.06	74.54	72.84	3.39	5.82	2.73	<0.46	0.38	<0.12	<0.12	0.26	<0.41
Gd	452.66	469.69	502.14	8.40	13.03	10.27	<0.42	1.53	<0.43	<1.32	<0.43	2.08
Tb	39.62	39.46	43.08	0.40	0.83	0.50	<0.06	<0.22	<0.06	<0.06	<0.06	0.42
Dy	151.62	158.92	180.28	1.69	4.65	1.91	<1.04	2.59	<1.02	<0.81	<0.26	2.14
Ho	23.35	25.01	27.38	0.37	0.77	0.17	<0.07	0.56	<0.06	<0.20	0.20	0.47
Er	49.93	57.58	63.86	0.51	1.87	<0.81	<1.13	3.09	<1.09	<0.29	0.52	2.75
Tm	6.17	7.05	7.19	0.11	0.41	<0.05	<0.06	0.37	0.07	<0.06	<0.28	0.11
Yb	39.27	37.75	45.08	0.86	2.26	0.98	0.53	1.72	<0.36	<0.37	1.22	3.43
Lu	5.80	5.40	6.67	0.08	0.25	<0.18	<0.06	0.33	<0.06	<0.19	0.18	0.35
Hf	1.86	1.12	1.47	<0.15	<0.30	<0.17	<0.21	0.76	<0.81	<0.21	<0.74	<0.21
Ta	0.06	0.06	<0.05	<0.05	<0.26	<0.06	0.28	3.22	0.28	<0.07	<0.24	0.08
W	<0.24	<0.24	0.24	0.42	<0.44	0.75	<0.31	0.79	<0.31	<0.97	<0.31	<0.32
Tl	<0.73	<0.82	<0.64	<0.75	<0.99	1.21	<0.70	<0.99	<0.85	<0.70	<0.76	<0.77
Pb	85.78	85.67	89.53	5.63	6.52	5.51	5.48	51.37	21.84	2.84	3.25	3.83
Bi	1.27	1.04	1.09	4.05	2.59	4.09	5.40	9.35	0.68	4.04	9.88	13.70
Th	14076.99	13681.70	14474.38	186.96	191.79	230.16	<0.06	1.22	<0.06	<0.06	<0.06	<0.20
U	652.74	684.67	785.64	50.21	86.00	56.77	0.19	0.75	0.11	0.91	3.49	1.67

Allanite, as one of the main accessory minerals in the studied pegmatites, suffered significant chemical transformation during the hydrothermal alteration and, according to the chemical composition, part of the mineral converts to REE-rich clinozoisite (see Table 3, Fig. 7). Because of the alteration, the chemistry of the studied allanite crystals shows a decrease in LREE and Fe incorporations, whereas Si, Al and Ca increase, resulting in REE-rich clinozoisite. The allanites occurring outside the alteration zone are also affected by epidote alteration, though to a lesser extent. The chemical composition of major, minor and trace elements in allanite is summarized in Tables 2, 3. The dominant REE in allanite are Ce, La and Nd. The Ce₂O₃ content is up to 8.5 wt.%, followed by La₂O₃ (6.9 wt.%),

Nd₂O₃ (2.5 wt.%) and ΣREE measured by LA-ICP-MS reaches up to 62.117 ppm. High contents of ThO₂ (up to 3.04 wt.%), U (956 ppm), Y (1151 ppm), Ga (706 ppm) and Ge (534 ppm) are established. A well-defined negative correlation between Ca and REE+Th, which illustrates the incorporation of REE and Th at the expense of Ca in A-site, is observed (Fig. 8a). Chondrite-normalized patterns for REE in allanite display LREE>HREE and a distinct negative Eu anomaly corresponding to the general REE-characteristics of allanite from igneous rocks (Gieré and Sorensen, 2004; Fig. 8b).

According to the major elements, the studied epidotes represent members of the clinozoisite-epidote solid solution, predominantly Fe-rich clinozoisite towards epidote in the second generation

Table 3
SEM-EDS representative analyses of allanite – REE-rich clinozoisite (wt.%). Abb.: ACT – actinides, mainly Th and U

Sample	Pch2A-1979	Pch2A-1980	Pch2A-1982	Pch2A-1983	Pch1p-2078	Pch1p-2079	Pch1p-2080	Pch1p-2088	Pch1p-2089	Pch1p-2101	Pch1p-2102	Pch1p-2109
	in the alteration zone				outside the alteration zone							
	crystal 1		crystal 2		crystal 3			crystal 4		crystal 5		grain
center		center	rim	center	rim		center	rim	rim	center		
SiO ₂	35.25	34.73	34.89	36.51	33.96	33.45	33.00	34.14	33.96	33.52	34.34	33.02
TiO ₂								0.57		0.30		0.33
Al ₂ O ₃	22.99	22.59	22.52	23.98	20.12	19.83	17.38	17.91	19.49	19.96	21.12	17.84
FeO	4.10	4.55	4.63	5.26	4.39	6.07	7.85	7.65	4.94	8.21	5.66	7.18
Fe ₂ O ₃	4.53	3.81	4.15	2.98	7.74	5.25	5.91	5.79	7.28	2.45	3.42	6.19
MgO	0.40	0.72	0.65	0.45	0.48		1.18	0.96	0.51		0.42	0.87
CaO	18.60	17.66	17.89	18.55	17.26	16.44	13.29	14.88	16.96	15.20	16.84	14.35
La ₂ O ₃	3.58	3.71	4.22	3.61	4.13	4.95	6.92	5.77	4.24	6.08	4.90	4.95
Ce ₂ O ₃	4.36	4.33	4.85	4.54	5.19	5.85	8.51	7.81	5.62	6.91	6.05	6.72
Nd ₂ O ₃	1.04	1.00			1.18	1.82	2.46	1.92	1.41	1.92	1.66	2.39
ThO ₂	1.66	2.47	3.04	1.55	0.98	1.26	2.22	1.93	1.52	1.88	1.47	1.30
Total	96.51	95.58	96.84	97.44	95.43	94.92	98.72	99.32	95.93	96.43	95.88	95.14
<i>apfu</i>												
Si (T)	3.020	3.023	3.014	3.064	3.004	3.028	3.015	3.037	3.020	3.042	3.047	3.034
Ti								0.038		0.020		0.023
Al	2.321	2.318	2.293	2.372	2.097	2.116	1.872	1.878	2.043	2.135	2.209	1.932
Fe ²⁺	0.294	0.332	0.334	0.369	0.324	0.459	0.561	0.569	0.367	0.623	0.420	0.498
Fe ³⁺	0.292	0.250	0.270	0.189	0.516	0.358	0.407	0.388	0.488	0.168	0.228	0.428
Mg	0.051	0.093	0.084	0.056	0.063	0.000	0.161	0.127	0.068	0.000	0.056	0.119
Σ M	2.959	2.993	2.982	2.986	3.000	2.933	3.000	3.000	2.966	2.946	2.913	3.000
Fe ²⁺					0.001		0.039					0.054
Ca	1.707	1.647	1.656	1.668	1.636	1.595	1.301	1.418	1.616	1.478	1.601	1.413
La	0.113	0.119	0.134	0.112	0.135	0.165	0.233	0.189	0.139	0.203	0.160	0.168
Ce	0.137	0.138	0.153	0.140	0.168	0.194	0.285	0.254	0.183	0.230	0.197	0.226
Nd	0.032	0.031	0.000	0.000	0.037	0.059	0.080	0.061	0.045	0.062	0.053	0.079
Th	0.032	0.049	0.060	0.030	0.020	0.026	0.046	0.039	0.031	0.039	0.030	0.027
Σ A	2.022	1.984	2.004	1.949	1.997	2.039	1.985	1.962	2.014	2.012	2.040	1.966
REE+ACT	0.314	0.337	0.348	0.281	0.360	0.444	0.644	0.544	0.398	0.534	0.439	0.500

(Armbruster *et al.*, 2006; see Fig. 7). Representative analyses of the studied minerals are listed in Tables 2, 4. The compositions of some major, minor and trace elements for both generations differ moderately. The content of CaO in the first generation epidote (epidote 1) is within 22.99–25.42 wt.%, Al_2O_3 is 22.03–29.41 wt.% (with average values of 26.01 wt.%), Fe_2O_3 ranges between 5.96 wt.% and 12.92 wt.% (with average 9.02 wt.%), whereas FeO is 0.00–0.85 wt.%. The first generation epidote is characterized by constant incorporations of MnO and traces of B, Zn, Ga, Sr, Y, Nb, Pb, Bi and U. The ΣREE reaches up to 57 ppm. A wide range of

Fig. 7. Composition of accessory allanite-(Ce), indicating alteration and transformation, and both clinozoisite-epidote generations represented on the classification diagram REE+Th vs. Al contoured with isolines of the ratio $F_{\text{ox}} = \text{Fe}^{3+}/(\text{Fe}^{3+} + \text{Fe}^{2+})$ (Petrík *et al.* 1995). The horizontal dashed line indicates the recommended chemical criterion to determine mineral as allanite, which is $\text{REE} + \text{ACT} > 0.5$ apfu.

elements is detected in most of the analyses with different magnitudes of concentration without characteristic patterns. A negative correlation between Al and Fe contents is observed in the composition of the analyzed crystals from both epidote generations (Fig. 9a). The sum of Fe and Al occupying *M*-sites is slightly lower (<3.00 apfu), probably due to the presence of other elements in the octahedral sites. On the other hand, Ca is generally in excess and, therefore, the Mn content should be attributed to the *M*-site, where a well-expressed negative correlation between Mn and Al+Fe is observed (Fig. 9b; Table 4). In single cases, Mn is redistributed in both *A*- and *M*-sites (see Table 4). Both epidote generations do not reveal a high concentration of REE, which otherwise have the ability to incorporate a significant amount of trace elements because of their crystal structure properties (Frei *et al.*, 2003, 2004). Comparatively increased REE contents are established only in crystals that have grown close to former allanite. Chondrite-normalized diagrams of both generations show relatively flat patterns with moderate depletion of LREE (Fig. 10).

The content of CaO in the studied second generation epidote (epidote 2) is similar to that in the first (20.83–25.27 wt.%). A slight decrease in Al_2O_3 (20.53–28.68 wt.% and average values of 24.53 wt.%) and an increase in Fe_2O_3 (6.19–17.94 wt.% with average values of 10.79 wt.%) and FeO (0.07–2.12 wt.%) are established compared to the first generation. The content of MnO is variable (see Table 4). Constant traces of B, V, Ga, Sr, Y, In, Ce, Pb and Bi are characteristic (see Table 2). Where epidote intersects or is formed close to allanite, the

Fig. 8. Correlation diagrams in allanite – REE-rich clinozoisite between Ca and REE+Th (a) and chondrite-normalised REE patterns of allanite – REE-rich clinozoisite out of the alteration zone (dark brown) and in the alteration zone (light brown) (b). Normalization values after Sun and McDonough (1989).

Fig. 9. Correlation between Al vs. $\text{Fe}_{(\text{Fe}^{2+} + \text{Fe}^{3+})}$ (a) and $\text{Al} + \text{Fe}_{(\text{Fe}^{2+} + \text{Fe}^{3+})}$ vs. Mn (b) contents for both epidote generations.

Table 4
SEM-EDS representative analyses of epidote (wt.%)

Type	epidote 1 pink					epidote 2 green							
Sample	Pch1-1911	Pch2a-1989	Pch2a-1999	Pch2a-2003	Pch2a-2021	Pch2a-2022	Pch2a-2023	Pch1-1892	Pch1-1917	Pch1-1926	Pch1-1927	Pch1-1928	Pch2a-1986
Details						one zonal crystal							
						pink core	green middle	green rim					
SiO ₂	38.58	38.83	39.61	39.14	39.15	37.78	38.16	37.99	38.2	38.09	38.64	38.19	38.03
Al ₂ O ₃	26.73	28.42	28.79	27.9	28.48	23.99	25.78	24.84	24.55	24.85	27.36	26.58	21.29
FeO			0.16	0.76	0.31								0.78
Fe ₂ O ₃	8.20	5.99	5.96	6.80	6.31	12.19	9.96	11.57	11.61	11.03	8.13	8.79	15.08
MnO	0.47	0.28	0.27	0.19	0.35	0.44	0.37						
CaO	23.85	24.2	24.43	23.73	23.93	23.2	23.65	24.3	23.88	24.13	24.35	24.06	23.22
Total	97.83	97.72	99.22	98.51	98.53	97.60	97.92	98.70	98.24	98.10	98.48	97.62	98.39
<i>apfu</i>													
Si (T)	3.020	3.016	3.030	3.029	3.021	3.008	3.002	2.979	3.012	3.001	2.998	2.998	3.042
Al	2.466	2.601	2.596	2.545	2.590	2.251	2.390	2.296	2.281	2.307	2.502	2.459	2.007
Fe			0.010	0.049	0.020								0.052
Fe ³⁺	0.484	0.351	0.344	0.396	0.367	0.731	0.590	0.683	0.690	0.655	0.475	0.520	0.909
Mn	0.031	0.018	0.017	0.010	0.023	0.017	0.020	0.000	0.000	0.000			0.000
Σ M	2.980	2.970	2.967	3.000	3.000	3.000	3.000	2.979	2.971	2.962	2.977	2.979	2.968
Ca	2.000	2.014	2.003	1.968	1.979	1.979	1.993	2.042	2.017	2.037	2.024	2.024	1.990
Mn				0.003		0.012	0.005						
Σ A				1.971		1.991	1.998						

content of REE (*e.g.*, Ce – 1961 ppm, La – 545 ppm, Nd – 252 ppm, Pr – 126 ppm), Cr, Sn, Th and U increases significantly.

The chlorite group minerals are a significant constituent in the hydrothermal alteration zone developed on pegmatites. The Fe/(Fe+Mg) ratio of the studied minerals ranges between 0.192 and 0.427. The MgO content is 17.58–24.61 wt.%, Al₂O₃ (16.33–17.36 wt.%), FeO (6.35–22.40 wt.%), Fe₂O₃

(0.55–4.55 wt.%), MnO (0.19–1.65 wt.%). According to the chemical composition, the chlorites belong to the clinocllore–chamosite solid solution series.

Chlorite thermometry

The chemical and structural properties of chlorite define the mineral as a potential geothermometer

Fig. 10. Chondrite-normalized REE diagram for epidote 1 pink (a) and 2 green (b) generations. The red lines demonstrate relatively high REE incorporation, which had been established in samples in close association with allanite. The shaded fields indicate range of values with average content (black line).

(Cathelineau, 1988; Jowett, 1991; De Caritat *et al.*, 1993). A possible procedure for chlorite geothermometry, based on the structural and compositional characteristics of the mineral, is the correlation between the occupancy of Al in the tetrahedral sites and formation temperature. According to Cathelineau (1988), the $Al_{(IV)}$ content in the tetrahedral site of chlorites increases with temperature. The studied chlorite from the epidote hydrothermal zone developed on pegmatites from the vicinity of the Strashimir Pb-Zn vein deposit yields a T° range of 223–266 °C.

U-Pb age of titanite

Two pegmatite titanites from the altered epidote hydrothermal zone yield a lower intercept U-Pb age of 39.9 ± 2.1 Ma (MSWD = 1.6) and 39.5 ± 3.1 Ma (MSWD = 0.61), respectively (Fig. 11a, b; Table 5; see also the Appendix). The titanites from the inner zone (apparently not hydrothermally overprinted) define a Discordia line with a lower intercept age at 39.5 ± 2.2 Ma (MSWD = 3.1) (Fig. 11c). As all three ages overlap in their uncertainty, a common lower intercept age is calculated using all analyses and an age of 39.3 ± 1.2 Ma (MSWD = 1.8) is defined (Fig. 11d). After the applied common ^{207}Pb correction (Andersen, 2002) for all three groups of the dated titanites, the weighted mean $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ age of the corrected concordant analyses is 39.84 ± 0.75 Ma (95% confidence, MSWD = 1.9).

DISCUSSION

The titanite crystals in the pegmatites from the vicinity of the Strashimir Pb-Zn deposit differ in

morphology, size, mineral association and chemical signatures. Three populations of the mineral are assigned. The first titanite population, established in pegmatites out of the hydrothermal zone, varies in size and shape and is presented mostly as anhedral, deformed and cracked up to 1 mm grains. Their chemistry displays a lower amount of Al and Fe compared to the titanites from the hydrothermal zone (population 3). Yttrium and Nb are detected only as traces by LA-ICP-MS. The geochemical features of this titanite have a wide range of Th/U, Dy/Yb_N and Lu/Hf ratios, lower ΣREE compared to those from the hydrothermal zone and positive Eu anomaly, which distinguishes them from population 3 and demonstrates mixed signatures likewise. The second titanite population differs in size, morphology and mineral association, but their small crystal size (up to 40 μm) did not allow further analytical studies.

Large (up to 3 mm) an- to euhedral, often zonal, crystals in association with epidote and chlorite (population 3) are observed in the alteration zone along the contact of the pegmatite with marble. The chemistry of these titanites shows greater content of Al and Fe and significant incorporation of Y and Nb, Ta, Sn, Zr, V and Th. The geochemical features of that titanite type, such as Th/U ratio and depletion of LREE relative to HREE, imply a hydrothermal origin of the mineral (Li *et al.*, 2010; Pan *et al.*, 2018; Scibiorski *et al.*, 2019, and references therein). However, the enhanced values for ΣREE , the high HFSE contents, such as Zr and Nb, the negative Eu anomaly and relatively high Lu/Hf ratio are characteristic for magmatic ones (Pan *et al.*, 2018, and references therein). Controversially, according to Zhu *et al.* (2022), Nb enrichment could be driven

Fig. 11. A) U-Pb age diagram for euhedral titanite in association with chlorite; b) U-Pb age diagram for anhedral titanite enclosed in epidote; c) U-Pb age diagram for titanite out of the alteration zone; d) U-Pb age diagram for all analyzed titanites.

by a hydrothermal event that causes remobilization and re-precipitation of such trace elements into hydrothermal titanites.

The chemical signatures of the studied mineral show a significant resemblance with some crystals from the Petrovitsa deposit, defined as hydrothermal, with similar U-Pb age of 39.2 ± 1.5 Ma (Milenkov *et al.*, 2022). The ambiguous characteristics of the studied titanites could be explained with the predisposition of the mineral to recrystallize during metamorphism, fluid flow and deformation, which can result in modification of its isotopic and trace elements composition (Gordon *et al.*, 2021; Moser *et al.*, 2022; Kavanagh-Lepage *et al.*, 2023).

According to Scibiorski *et al.* (2019), Eu, LREE and Th/U are useful to discriminate between titanite populations, but not necessarily as growth process indicators. The trace element properties of titanite are controlled by complex factors such as crystallization sequence, dissolution-precipitation, whole-rock and reactive subsystem composition, pressure and temperature. Thus, the mineral might reveal both LREE and HREE enrichment or depletion

and negative or positive Eu anomaly (Storey *et al.*, 2007; Bruand *et al.*, 2014; Scibiorski *et al.*, 2019, Scibiorski and Cawood, 2021).

The depletion of LREE in titanite could be a result of remobilization of the LREE into other LREE phases during fluid pulses or in case of concurrent crystallization of LREE-rich minerals such as allanite and/or monazite (Papapavlou *et al.*, 2017). Titanite might be enriched in LREE if it grows after HREE-incorporating minerals such as garnet and zircon (Scibiorski *et al.*, 2019) The Eu anomaly is also affected by the crystallization sequence and the influence of plagioclase in the mineral association.

The studied titanites from a hydrothermal zone are LREE-depleted with clear negative Eu anomaly that suggests crystallization of this population after plagioclases, allanite and monazite. The titanite population observed outside of the hydrothermal zone has HREE depletion, low REE and positive Eu anomaly that could be a sign of an early crystallization.

Despite the established chemical and mineralogical differences between the titanite populations,

Table 5
Obtained data for the U-Pb age of titanite

Pb/U	Final 207_235	Int2SE	Final 206_238	Int2SE	ErrorCorr	Final 207_206	Int2SE	Final Age207_235	Int2SE	Final Age206_238	Int2SE
Epidote hydrothermal zone, sample Pch1											
Pch1_1	0.910	0.110	0.0152	0.0014	0.076	0.515	0.090	647	62	97.3	8.7
Pch1_2	1.050	0.140	0.0152	0.0016	0.085	0.580	0.100	692	72	97.0	10.0
Pch1_3	1.020	0.100	0.0148	0.0012	0.025	0.533	0.067	691	51	94.5	7.9
Pch1_4	0.798	0.098	0.0116	0.0010	0.144	0.530	0.071	569	54	74.0	6.5
Pch1_5	1.010	0.130	0.0138	0.0012	0.093	0.567	0.096	673	71	88.4	7.7
Pch1_6	0.584	0.090	0.0100	0.0010	0.048	0.433	0.070	447	55	63.9	6.3
Pch1_7	0.542	0.063	0.0104	0.0008	0.001	0.403	0.054	425	42	66.7	5.2
Pch1_8	0.860	0.100	0.0132	0.0011	0.143	0.523	0.079	599	58	84.4	6.9
Pch1_9	0.392	0.049	0.0103	0.0006	0.024	0.288	0.040	329	37	66.0	3.9
Pch1_10	0.800	0.120	0.0137	0.0015	0.031	0.490	0.100	564	65	87.7	9.6
Pch1_11	0.720	0.110	0.0133	0.0012	0.091	0.419	0.068	517	63	85.1	7.4
Pch1_12	0.592	0.078	0.0112	0.0010	0.116	0.427	0.069	460	54	71.6	6.2
Pch1_13	0.235	0.027	0.0083	0.0004	0.342	0.207	0.024	209	23	53.2	2.7
Pch1_14	0.297	0.039	0.0083	0.0005	0.037	0.263	0.036	255	30	53.4	3.1
Pch1_15	0.790	0.110	0.0131	0.0012	0.133	0.451	0.068	563	63	84.1	7.7
Pch1_16	0.591	0.078	0.0114	0.0008	0.218	0.389	0.048	449	49	73.1	5.2
Pch1_17	0.191	0.026	0.0075	0.0005	0.031	0.193	0.028	175	23	47.9	2.9
Pch1_18	0.432	0.057	0.0102	0.0009	0.028	0.351	0.054	364	44	65.1	5.6
Pch1_19	0.603	0.071	0.0109	0.0008	0.061	0.448	0.064	464	48	69.8	5.0
Pch1_20	0.193	0.024	0.0074	0.0004	0.260	0.203	0.029	176	20	47.2	2.4
Pch1_21	0.186	0.024	0.0074	0.0004	0.079	0.193	0.029	169	20	47.4	2.6
Pch1_22	0.195	0.021	0.0072	0.0005	0.120	0.211	0.029	179	18	46.1	2.9
Pch1_23	0.616	0.083	0.0106	0.0009	0.014	0.434	0.069	468	52	68.0	5.7
Pch1_24	0.167	0.025	0.0078	0.0004	0.014	0.167	0.027	153	22	49.9	2.8
Pch1_25	0.517	0.068	0.0101	0.0010	0.206	0.383	0.056	412	46	64.5	6.1
Pch1_26	0.466	0.072	0.0103	0.0009	0.078	0.363	0.066	365	49	66.0	5.9
Epidote hydrothermal zone, sample Pch2											
Pech2_1	0.485	0.060	0.0097	0.0007	0.076	0.375	0.052	385	42	62.5	4.2
Pech2_2	0.467	0.061	0.0092	0.0006	0.307	0.363	0.044	371	40	58.8	3.9
Pech2_3	0.262	0.032	0.0080	0.0005	0.011	0.242	0.030	229	25	51.4	3.1
Pech2_4	0.219	0.032	0.0074	0.0005	0.047	0.221	0.036	195	27	47.8	3.1
Pech2_5	0.264	0.038	0.0081	0.0005	0.242	0.239	0.035	230	30	51.9	3.3
Pech2_6	0.160	0.029	0.0069	0.0004	0.106	0.188	0.036	152	27	44.0	2.5
Pech2_7	0.247	0.031	0.0078	0.0005	0.153	0.248	0.035	222	27	50.3	3.0
Pech2_8	0.276	0.044	0.0083	0.0007	0.053	0.246	0.044	241	35	53.2	4.2
Pech2_9	0.198	0.031	0.0076	0.0005	0.045	0.201	0.034	180	26	48.5	3.0
Pech2_10	0.252	0.036	0.0080	0.0005	0.068	0.241	0.035	221	28	51.6	3.1
Central pegmatite visibly not hydrothermally overprinted zone											
TitPech_1	0.766	0.072	0.0125	0.0007	0.015	0.471	0.051	563	40	80.0	4.5
TitPech_2	0.360	0.029	0.0089	0.0003	0.127	0.298	0.024	311	21	56.8	2.0
TitPech_3	0.430	0.030	0.0100	0.0005	0.040	0.325	0.029	365	20	64.1	3.1
TitPech_4	0.325	0.026	0.0091	0.0003	0.261	0.252	0.020	286	20	58.4	2.2
TitPech_5	0.275	0.020	0.0080	0.0004	0.165	0.244	0.019	245	16	51.3	2.2
TitPech_6	0.980	0.100	0.0161	0.0010	0.451	0.453	0.044	686	54	103.1	6.2
TitPech_7	0.636	0.058	0.0120	0.0007	0.124	0.375	0.037	492	37	76.8	4.4
TitPech_8	0.146	0.015	0.0074	0.0003	0.266	0.143	0.015	137	13	47.7	1.9
TitPech_9	0.177	0.021	0.0072	0.0003	0.270	0.171	0.019	166	18	46.0	1.7
TitPech_10	0.158	0.019	0.0072	0.0003	0.211	0.155	0.018	148	16	46.3	1.7
TitPech_11	1.081	0.075	0.0152	0.0007	0.081	0.524	0.043	737	38	97.4	4.3
TitPech_12	0.645	0.046	0.0110	0.0004	0.158	0.435	0.031	503	29	70.5	2.5
TitPech_13	0.214	0.019	0.0075	0.0003	0.009	0.218	0.022	195	16	48.0	1.9
TitPech_15	1.260	0.120	0.0161	0.0011	0.065	0.608	0.077	813	54	102.8	6.8
TitPech_19	1.218	0.097	0.0154	0.0011	0.136	0.625	0.062	808	45	98.3	6.7

they indicate similar U-Pb ages that overlap in their uncertainties (39.9 ± 2.1 Ma and 39.5 ± 3.1 Ma in the hydrothermal epidote-chlorite zone and 39.5 ± 2.2 Ma in the central and visibly hydrothermally not overprinted zone). Having in mind the error uncertainties, the timeframe of the titanite growth is between ~ 42 Ma and 37.3 Ma. However, the lower limit seems overestimated, as the cooling history of the hanging wall (through ~ 300 °C) from Rb-Sr and Ar-Ar dating is constrained at 38 Ma (Kaiser Rohrmeier *et al.*, 2013). These data suggest titanite growth in a granitic pegmatite vein, whereas the hydrothermal fluids were either extracted from the same melt or related to later overprinting processes that did not influence the U-Pb isotope system of the mineral significantly.

The studied allanite is determined as a Ce-dominant member with high incorporations of La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Th, Y, Ga and Ge. According to the recommended nomenclature of epidote-group minerals (Armbruster *et al.*, 2006), the approved chemical requirement to determine allanite is REE+ACT (actinides, mainly Th and U) > 0.5 apfu. The obtained data for the chemical composition of the studied allanite indicate REE+ACT contents in the range of 0.269–0.644 apfu. The reduced REE, as well as the increased content of Al, Si, and Ca, in the majority of the analyzed crystals indicate a hydrothermal alteration of the allanite. The processes of leaching and migration of REE during fluid-mineral interaction result in a chemical destabilization of the mineral and correspond to the allanite/epidote transformation as it was proposed by Poitrasson (2002). The REE enrichment of the late epidotes precipitated on or close to allanite crystals reveals the remarkably short transport of the REE (as also noticed by Gros *et al.*, 2020).

The complex textural zoning of the allanite demonstrates additional indications of dissolution and recrystallization resulting from repeated interactions of primary grains with late- to post-magmatic fluids, which produced a patchwork of domains with variable composition. The alteration of the mineral can be facilitated additionally by the presence of cracks and/or by its metamictization degree due to the incorporation of radiogenic elements in the crystal structure (Gieré and Sorensen, 2004).

Two epidote generations along with chlorite are the main hydrothermal alteration products that affected the contact zone between the pegmatite and marbles from the vicinity of the Strashimir Pb-Zn vein deposit. This mineralization is a result of a multiphase or long-term mineral formation during the extensive hydrothermal activity in the region.

The first generation epidotes precipitated in an Al- and Ca-rich environment with small portions of Fe. Later, the hydrothermal fluids became enriched in Fe and the second epidote generation was deposited. This mineralization is characterized by the low but constant incorporation of Mn, especially in the first generation, which outlines the manganese geochemical specialization of the hydrothermal mineralization in the entire Madan region. However, manganese-containing minerals from the epidote group, such as piemontite, have been documented only in the Laki and Davidkovo ore districts (Stoinova, 1963; Marinova, 1992).

Both epidote generations differ in morphology, color and chemical signatures. Chemically, both generations are determined as members of the clinzoisite–epidote series, predominantly Fe³⁺-rich clinzoisite. By the increase in Fe in the fluid, epidote end members with Fe₂O₃ composition up to 17.93 wt.% (corresponding to 1–1.1 apfu) are established in later epidote generations.

The first generation epidote occurs as red to dark pink crystals and shows distinct red-violet pleochroism, which according to Bonazzi and Menchetti (2004) is characteristic basically for manganese (*i.e.*, Mn³⁺-bearing) epidote or clinzoisite, contrasted to manganite (*i.e.*, Mn²⁺-bearing) members. The pink coloring and piemontite-like pleochroism of the epidotes could be manifested even with very low Mn³⁺ incorporation (Armbruster *et al.*, 2006; Katerinopoulou *et al.*, 2014). According to the recommended epidote-group nomenclature (Armbruster *et al.*, 2006), Mn preferentially enters into the *M*-sites as Mn³⁺ and Mn²⁺, as well as into *A*-sites as Mn²⁺. According to the aforementioned suggestions and considering the data from the present study, the most probable Mn occupancy in the majority of the studied crystals is in the *M*-site as either Mn³⁺ and/or Mn²⁺. The latter is due to the deficit at the *M*-sites and the excess at the *A*-site, and regarding the characteristic reddish hue of the minerals as well. In a small number of analyses, a deficiency in both *M*- and *A*-sites suggests the redistribution of Mn among both positions. The first generation epidotes are characterized by a relatively constant Mn content compared to the second. Even a small amount of Mn (up to 0.053 apfu) is sufficient to act as a chromophore and to result in red-pink coloring, despite the iron content. However, the increased amount of Fe in the second generation significantly prevails and suppresses the Mn chromophore role.

Both epidote generations have a moderate concentration of REE. Comparatively increased REE contents were established only in crystals and grains

proximal to the earlier accessories (e.g., allanite), while REE depletion in the latter is documented.

CONCLUSIONS

Considering the mineralogical and geochemical features of the studied pegmatite from the vicinity of the Strashimir Pb-Zn deposit, it could be assigned to the petrogenetic NYF-family or mixed type marked by a Nb>Ta, Ti, Y, Sc, REE, Zr, U, Th, F array of typical elements according to the classification of the granitic pegmatites of Černý and Ecrít (2005).

Three titanite populations are distinguished based on their occurrence, mineral association and chemical properties. Nevertheless, the U-Pb age determinations of two of the populations (populations 1 and 3) indicate close timing of formation that probably refers to either a pegmatite stage or post-magmatic events. The pegmatite formation age could be crosschecked by U-Pb geochronology on zircon.

Considering the chemical properties of the studied accessory minerals, it becomes obvious that elements such as Th and LREE are preferentially incorporated in the crystal structure of allanite, while V, U, Nb, Y, Sn are favorably incorporated in the titanites.

The pegmatite is affected by hydrothermal alteration without any signs of ore mineralization, despite the close proximity to the Strashimir Pb-Zn deposit with significant vein ore-bodies.

The main hydrothermal mineral association is epidote–chlorite–carbonate. The epidote is manifested in two distinct generations. Both are defined as members of the clinozoisite–epidote series, reaching epidote members in the second generation, which indicates the enrichment in Fe in the later fluid. Trace element signatures of epidotes reveal

minor REE concentrations, although the crystal structure of the epidote-group minerals incorporates such elements. The REE contents in the studied minerals are elevated in individual grains formed next to accessory allanite.

The chlorite geothermometry reveals temperature of formation in the hydrothermal zone between 223–266 °C.

Due to the hydrothermal event, the studied allanite-(Ce) suffered alteration and is partly or entirely transformed into REE-rich epidote-clinozoisite, causing depletion in REE and Fe and enrichment in Si, Al and Ca. Because of the limited mobility of REE in fluids, after leaching these elements are incorporated in crystalizing epidotes nearby.

The pegmatite from the vicinity of the Strashimir Pb-Zn deposit contains a number of REE-bearing accessory minerals (e.g., allanite, titanite, apatite, zircon), and therefore could be a subject to further scientific exploration for a better understanding of the processes influencing the concentration of the trace elements in pegmatites.

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APPENDIX

U-Pb geochronological data (available online at https://www.geologica-balcanica.eu/sites/default/files/supplementary/Georgieva_Geol_Balc_52-2_2023_Appendix.rar.)

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